

Cytotoxic T lymphocyte antigen-4 (CTLA-4)

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Abstract

Cytotoxic T lymphocyte antigen 4 (CTLA-4) is a T lymphocyte surface molecule that plays a role in regulating the immune response. This molecule also plays an important role in regulating T cell activation and can limit the T cell response in accordance with inflammatory conditions. CTLA-4 Ig is a soluble chimeric protein and has a negative regulatory function in the body. When a foreign substance tries to enter the body, T cells become active and if this response shows excessive activation, it can damage normal and healthy cells and tissues, so it should be kept under control. It has been reported that genetic diversity in CTLA-4 may play a role in the development of autoimmune diseases. It is recommended that CTLA-4 be investigated in more detail to examine its effects by looking at the levels of CTLA-4 in the course of autoimmune diseases. It is thought that further investigation of CTLA-4 may contribute to immunotherapy and cancer treatments.

Keywords: CTLA-4, T lymphocyte, autoimmune disease, Cytotoxic T lymphocyte, CD4, CD8

INTRODUCTION

Cytotoxic T lymphocyte antigen-4 (CTLA-4) is a T lymphocyte surface molecule involved in regulating immune response, and the various polymorphisms of the gene region in which this molecule is synthesized have been identified in different populations. CTLA-4 points are the negative regulator of T cell immune function. CTLA-4 is thought to regulate primarily T cell proliferation in the immune response in lymph nodes. This molecule also plays an important role in regulating T cell activation and can limit T cell response in accordance with inflammation conditions. It has been reported that genetic diversity in CTLA-4 may play a role in the development of autoimmune diseases. The level of sCTLA-4, a form of CTLA-4 (soluble cytotoxic T lymphocyte antigen 4), has been determined to increase in thyroiditis, myasthenia gravis, systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE), and systemic sclerosis.¹⁻⁵

Lymphocytes account for 20-25% of leukocytes in the bloodstream. It is rounded in blood smears and has different shapes in connective tissue. Lymphocytes are slightly larger than erythrocytes and are measured 8-10 µm in diameter in blood smears. Lymphocytes are structures whose nuclei are stained blue-purple with blood dyes. Its cytoplasm is too small to appear in the microscope. Based on the amount and diameter of cytoplasm, they are divided into small, medium, and large. Small type lymphocytes are between 6-8 µm, while medium-sized lymphocytes are found in small numbers in the bloodstream. Large type lymphocytes are 18 µm in diameter. The blood includes mostly the small type lymphocytes. The largest-appearing lymphocytes are

lymphoblast. Lymphocytes appear similar when examined under a microscope but are divided functionally into two groups, T and B lymphocytes. B lymphocytes are responsible for humoral immunity in the immune system, and T lymphocytes are responsible for cellular immunity.⁶⁻¹⁰

T lymphocytes originate from progenitor cells in the bone marrow and develop into T lymphocytes in the thymus. Progenitor cells that migrate to the thymus turn to T cell development. In humans, T cell development depends on the IL-7. The immunoglobulin receptor is not present in the membrane of T lymphocytes. Instead, the cell membrane of T lymphocytes contains the polypeptide T cell receptor (TCR). T lymphocytes gain receptors in the glycoprotein structure attached to the cell surface to recognize the antigens they will encounter in the thymus. These receptor molecules, named after the CD (Cluster of Differentiation) system, are called T lymphocyte surface antigens. T lymphocytes are split in two according to the CD4(Cluster of Differentiation 4) and CD8(Cluster of Differentiation 8) surface antigens they carry in their membranes. One-third of circulating T lymphocytes carry CD8 and two-thirds carry CD4 surface antigens. An antigen entering the organism is processed by the antigen-presenting cells and bound with the MHC (Major Histocompatibility Complex) molecule and presented to the lymphocytes, and a solid structure of the newly formed complex is provided by the CD molecule. The T cell receptor does not act alone to transfer the first impulse into the cell but makes it through preserved, transmembrane proteins called CD3, which transforms connection with the peptide MHC complex

into signals by transferring it into the cell. T lymphocytes send signals in the protein structure called cytokines in response to antigenic stimulation. The resulting signals stimulate the proliferation and differentiation of T lymphocytes, B lymphocytes, and macrophages while gathering and activating inflammation-related cells such as macrophages.¹⁰⁻¹⁶

There are three types of T lymphocytes. These are expressed as helper T cells (Th), Cytotoxic T lymphocyte (CTL, CD8 T cell) and regulatory T cells (Treg). CD4⁺ (T helper lymphocyte) first joins circulation, forming as a T cell in the thymus. These cells that encounter their antigens differentiate then into specific groups of T lymphocytes, driven by the cytokine environment. CD8 destroys tumor cells or infected cells. Treg constitute 5-10% of CD4⁺ T cells, an important member of cellular immunity in human peripheral blood. It has been highlighted that Tregs play an important role in suppressing immune responses to autoimmune diseases and cancer.¹⁶⁻¹⁹

Cytotoxic T lymphocytes (CTLs) can destroy microorganisms, and can also be an attack cell that kills the body's own cells. Therefore, these cells are also called killer cells. This group of T lymphocytes with CD8 molecules on their surface is also called CD8 cells. Through receptor proteins found on cytotoxic cells, they easily recognize and kill non-normal cells by attaching to the organism or cell that carries the antigen they are specifically attached to. CTL secrete proteins called perforin which create large holes in the cell membrane of the cells it attacks, and interstitial fluid rapidly accumulates into the cell from these holes. Alongside the interstitial fluid, the lymphotoxin and proteases secreted by CTL also enter the cell and cause cell lysis. These cells have no phagocytosis effects, so they are not capable of intracellular killing. After the stimulation of the cytotoxic granules are directed to the microtubule system at an extraordinary velocity, moving to the point where the target has come into contact with the cytotoxic T lymphocyte. This process provides the specificity of the target's recognition by TCR and limits the damage of natural killer cells to themselves and the environment.^{6,8,10,20}

History and structure of CTLA-4

Cytotoxic T lymphocyte antigen-4 was first described in 1987 by Pierre Golstein and his colleagues. CTLA-4 is one of the secondary signaling molecules involved in the Ig superfamily, which serves by increasing the receptors present on T cells. The molecular weight of the membrane CTLA-4 molecule is 45 kDa. Cytotoxic-T-lymphocyte-antigen-4 is structurally expressed in regulatory T cells and is a negative immune regulator that regulates activated T cells. CTLA-4 inhibits T cell activation with a variety of suppressive functions, including regulation, adhesion, and control of the mobility of the inhibitory function of Treg cells in conjunction with CD28. It also plays an important role in suppressing Treg cells and maintaining peripheral tolerance.^{21,22}

It has been reported that the CTLA-4 protein is in a homodimer structure and that the proteins that make up this structure are bound together by disulfide bonds, and that each monomeric peptide binds to B7-1 and B7-2 molecules at high affinity.²³ Ling et al.²⁴ reconstructed the sequence of CTLA-4 proteins in humans and

mice. They revealed that the 244 amino acids contained in the CTLA-4 protein of humans were highly similar to the content of the CTLA-4 protein of mice. Magistrelli et al.²⁵ determined that inactive T lymphocytes in human peripheral blood express an alternative form of the CTLA-4 molecule by using the real-time polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR). Oaks et al.⁵ found another form of the CTLA-4 molecule and reported that it contains 137 amino acids. It was later found that this was soluble T lymphocyte (sCTLA-4) and contained only 22 out of 34 cytoplasmic tails compared to the sequence of molecular CTLA-4 (CTLA-4 TM).²⁵

While the actual function of the sCTLA-4 molecule is not fully known, it is thought it could act as a receptor. It is thought that sCTLA-4 prevents the interaction of B7 with CD28 in the inactive T cell, while it can prevent the interaction of B7 with CTLA 4 in the activated T cell. sCTLA-4 have been found on the spleen, lymph nodes CD4 and CD8 T lymphocytes, B lymphocytes, and monocytes.⁵³

CTLA-4 Gene Polymorphism

Cytotoxic T lymphocyte antigen-4 Ig is a dissolvable chimeric protein. It binds to secondary stimulant molecules, such as B7-1 and B7-2 found on cells that offer antigens. It inhibits the CD28 molecule. CD80 and CD86 molecules are the ligands of CTLA-4, but they have also been described as the ligands of CD28 that is its homologous. There are two alleles in each gene region, one from the father and the other from the mother. If alleles differ between individuals in a locus, it is called polymorphism. If a relationship between polymorphism and disease is found in genetic studies, it should not be interpreted as being directly linked to the disease. Polymorphisms are seen at the rate of 1/1000 base pairs on DNA, while this ratio is 1/2500 base pairs for protein-coding regions. Numerous polymorphisms of the CTLA-4 gene have been identified, but among them, the most commonly reported of these are:

- 1) Exon 1: It encodes the peptide signal.
- 2) Exon 2: It encodes the noncellular area, including the CD80 and CD86 binding zones and the dimerization zone.
- 3) Exon 3: It encodes the transmembrane area.
- 4) Exon 4: It encodes the cytoplasmic tail.²⁶⁻³⁰

Isoforms of CTLA-4

The gene encoding the CTLA-4 molecule is located in the q33 band of chromosome 2. Exon 1 of the gene encodes the precursor peptide of CTLA-4, exon 2 the ligand-binding portion, exon 3 the transmembrane portion, and exon 4 the cytoplasmic tail. The product of this gene, CTLA-4, consists of a total of 149 amino acids. When the transcription product of the CTLA-4 gene is cut in different ways, three different CTLA-4 molecules appear. Of these, what is defined in man is as follows:

- 1) Full-length CTLA-4 molecule (fCTLA-4 or CTLA-4) synthesized from mRNA containing all exons.
- 2) Soluble CTLA-4 molecule (sCTLA-4), synthesized from mRNA lacking exon 3.
- 3) CTLA-4 molecule synthesized from mRNA containing

only exon 1 and exon 4.³¹

Major Functions of the CTLA-4 Molecule

- CTLA-4 acts as a negative regulator of T cell activation, counterbalancing the stimulatory signal provided by CD28.
- It prevents the cell cycle from advancing. It leads to inhibition of transcription factors such as NF- κ B (Nuclear factor kappa β and NFAT(Nuclear factor of activated T-cells).
- It prevents cytokine production and cell proliferation.
- It increases cell motility.
- It reduces contact time of T-cell-APC (antigen-presenting cell).³²⁻³⁵

AUTOIMMUNITY AND CTLA-4

CTLA-4 is a homolog of CD28, another T cell surface receptor. CD80 and CD86 molecules are ligands of CTLA-4, but they have also been identified as ligands of its homolog, CD28. CTLA-4 binds to CD80 and CD86 ligands found in antigen-presenting cells, like CD28, but their binding affinities differ. CTLA-4's binding affinity to the B7 molecule is 100 times greater than that of CD28. Consequently, CTLA-4 cannot generate a signal on its own, but it prevents the positive effect of CD28. The CD28 molecule also binds to the B7 molecule, enabling T cell activation.³⁶⁻³⁹

Competition of CTLA-4 with CD28

CD28 enables necessary T-cell responses to pathogens while activating regulatory mechanisms necessary for autoimmunity prevention. CTLA-4 is the main inhibitory molecule of the immune system, both by keeping the regulatory T cell's suppressor property under control and by inhibiting the effector T cell functions.⁴⁰

Inhibitory signal creation by CTLA-4

CTLA-4 increases the number of inhibitory molecules, such as tyrosine phosphatases. As a result, positive signals from CD28 are blocked and the T cell is suppressed.²⁹

Activation of T Regulator Cells

T regulatory cells (Tregs) are a small group (5-10%) of peripheral CD4+ T cells that express CD25 in addition to CD4. Unlike inactivated T cells, these cells also continuously express CTLA-4, therefore it is thought that the suppressor activity of Tregs can be increased via CTLA-4.⁴¹⁻⁴³

Stimulating Indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase Pathway

Indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase enzyme (IDO) inhibits T cell activation by breaking down tryptophan intracellularly, and causes T cells to undergo apoptosis. CTLA-4 stimulates this enzyme pathway. It has also been reported that CTLA-4 Ig fusion protein leads to 'up-regulation' of the IDO enzyme.⁴²

Impact of CTLA-4 on Intracellular Protein Traffic

CTLA-4 has a very strong internalization signal in its cytoplasmic portion. According to this model, CTLA-4 can easily circulate within the cell and, during this process, removes some important fragments from the TCR complex, thereby exerting its inhibitory effect.²⁹

Role of CTLA-4 in Autoimmune Diseases

Many experimental models support that T cells create energy against their own antigens. In mice, when a high level of B7 molecule was expressed, an autoimmune reaction appeared to develop. It was noted that autoreactive T cells are activated if secondary signals are allowed to be shown, and it was stated that if energy is eliminated, autoreactive T cells are activated and that by blocking the CTLA-4 molecule in mice, the mouse develops immunity to its own tissues. These results indicate that the CTLA-4 molecule operating as an inhibitory receptor is tasked with autoreactive T cell control. Many autoimmune diseases (e.g. SLE, Hashimoto Thyroid (HT), graves) that develop in the human with abnormalities of secondary signaling molecules or CTLA-4 molecules have been shown recently. It was recorded that while sCTLA-4 levels were low in normal human serum, its level increased in autoimmune diseases (graves, myasthenia gravis, SLE, Type 1 diabetes mellitus (Type 1 DM), systemic sclerosis, celiac disease, autoimmune pancreatitis, primary biliary cirrhosis).^{44,45,46,53}

While there have been many studies investigating the association of CTLA-4 gene polymorphisms with Graves' disease (GD), they targeted usually the exon 1 and promoter region. Therefore, the relationship between CTLA-4 gene polymorphism and GD is likely to be clarified by more intensive research of other polymorphic regions.⁴⁷

The study to support the functions of CD80 and CTLA-4, which are thought to have roles in Nephrotic Syndrome (NS), found that CD80 was increasing in urine and blood during the period of proteinuria in NS. sCTLA-4 was also found to be increasing in blood and urine at the time of proteinuria. It has been reported that further studies are needed to reveal why CD80 and sCTLA-4 are increasing in NS. A study investigating the role of -318C>T, +49A>G ve CT60A>G polymorphisms of CTLA-4 gene revealed that there was no difference between psoriasis vulgaris cases and control groups in terms of allele frequency and genotype distribution of -318C T polymorphism and that this polymorphism was not associated with psoriasis vulgaris disease.^{2,48}

In a study investigating the role of sCTLA-4 serum levels in the pathogenesis of ankylosing spondylitis (AS) disease, a statistically significant increase was found between disease groups, control groups and AS patients ($p < 0.001$). Although no significant association between sCTLA-4 levels and disease activation was identified in AS patients, it was suggested that these cytokine levels can be used in the early diagnosis of AS. In a study investigating the effects of A/G polymorphism of CTLA-4 gene on the clinical course of patients with Type 1 DM CTLA-4 49 A/G polymorphism was not recorded as affecting the risk of developing Type 1 DM in Turkish children. In a study on MYG1 gene in vitiligo disease, MYG1 gene rs1465073 polymorphism and CTLA-4 gene rs231775 polymorphism were evaluated in 106 patients diag-

sed with vitiligo and 97 controls, and it was noted that MYG1 gene rs1465073 polymorphism was associated with vitiligo, but there was no relationship between CTLA-4 gene rs231775 polymorphism and vitiligo. The association of CTLA-4 49A/G and SEPS1 105G/A polymorphisms with Hashimoto thyroid was researched in a study, the DNA samples isolated from peripheral blood leukocytes of 55 patients diagnosed with HT and 50 healthy individuals were amplified by PCR using specific primers containing CTLA-4 49A/G and SEPS1 -105G/A regions. As a result, it was said that CTLA-4 49 A/G polymorphism was not effective in the Turkish population in HT pathogenesis, but it was stated that more cases are needed to reach a definitive conclusion.^{49,50,51,52}

CONCLUSION

Cytotoxic T lymphocyte antigen-4 Ig is a dissolvable chimeric protein and has a negative regulatory role in the body. When a foreign substance tries to enter the body, T cells become active, and if the resulting response is too activated, it can damage normal and healthy cells and tissues, so it must be contained. At this stage, the immune system activates negative regulation, and the CTLA-4 molecule present in the cell is activated and exported to the cell surface. The CTLA-4 molecule binds to the B7 molecule, as does the CD28 molecule. As a result of binding CTLA-4 to CD28, T activation is ceased. The T-cells perform their tasks thanks to CTLA-4's inhibiting system and move to the resting phase. It is recommended that CTLA-4 should be further investigated to examine its effect by researching the levels of CTLA-4 in the course of autoimmune diseases. It is thought that further investigation of CTLA-4 may contribute to immunotherapy and cancer treatments.

MAIN POINT

It has been reported that genetic diversity in CTLA-4 may play a role in the development of autoimmune diseases. It is recommended that CTLA-4 be investigated in more detail to examine its effects by looking at the levels of CTLA-4 in the course of autoimmune diseases. It is thought that further investigation of CTLA-4 may contribute to immunotherapy and cancer treatments.

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